

Farmer Clusters: The role of a Facilitator and expert support

Policy recommendations

To promote Farmer Clusters as an effective approach to improve biodiversity, environmental outcomes, and sustainability across farm landscapes, the following policies are recommended:

- **Initiation of a Facilitation Fund throughout the EU Member States** that would provide:
 - Easy-to-access, long-term funding (5-10 years) to Facilitators or Facilitation teams that would work with farmers within Farmer Clusters. The funding would allow one-to-one or group advice to farmers and allow Facilitators to set up training/workshops for farmers in areas of biodiversity conservation interest to the farmers.
 - The funding would also allow landscape scale biodiversity monitoring and evidence gathering.
- **Clear financial support available from each Member State** for biodiversity conservation activities on farmland and specifically within Farmer Clusters:
 - Easy-to-access funding for biodiversity-friendly measures for individual farms and/or farms within a Farmer Cluster that Facilitators can apply for on behalf of the farmers.
 - Specific guidance from each Member State on what activities are funded at a national or regional level, and how applications can be made.

The role of the Facilitator in a successful Farmer Cluster

Agri-environment schemes (AES) aim to reverse declines in farmland biodiversity, however, their uptake and impact varies widely. Farmer Clusters offer an alternative pathway. The Facilitator, an advisor who works with all the farmers in the Cluster to help them achieve their biodiversity goals, provides individual guidance to each farmer in the Cluster, resulting in tailored biodiversity-friendly activities initiated across the landscape. Farmer Clusters bear the potential to motivate farmers to engage in collaborative efforts and can also increase knowledge about biodiversity. By working together under the guidance of a skilled Facilitator, farmers can tackle landscape-level restoration and have a greater impact than any one individual could accomplish alone. Using a “bottom-up” approach, farmers identify their conservation priorities and choose which practices to implement collectively. This is a novel and impactful way to address global issues such as biodiversity conservation at the landscape scale.

Approach and results

The **EU Horizon 2020 project FRAMEwork** explored the potential to replicate the Farmer Cluster model across Europe to enhance farmland biodiversity at a continental scale. Between 2020 and 2021, eleven clusters were established in eight countries: the UK, Austria, the Czech Republic, Estonia, France, Italy, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, and Spain, and varied in size, farming system, organisational structure, and the degree of connectivity between farms. Biodiversity-friendly practices

introduced by the Farmer Clusters include the introduction of wildflower margins, meadow restoration, hedgerow and tree planting, and the installation of bat and bird boxes. Leaning on experiences from the FRAMEwork project, this policy brief explains the significance of the Facilitator during system network analyses of the Farmer Clusters, and how their role is integral to the system as a whole.

Evidence of Facilitator Significance

Through advanced systems analysis, the importance of the Facilitator and their role in the success of a Farmer Cluster has been identified, directly or via critical interpretation of research results. The findings from the social-ecological network analysis highlight the critical role of Cluster facilitation in enabling biodiversity-sensitive farming, especially in contexts where value-chain actors are absent, reinforcing the need for sustained support for Facilitators to ensure collective action and ecological benefits at landscape scale (Ndlovu et al., 2024). Specifically, network indicators for the analysed Clusters (Luxembourg, Scotland and Italy, the latter showed in the figure nearby) showed that Farmer Clusters (red dot in the figure) serve as hubs for distributing knowledge, practices, and resources. In this context, Facilitators play a crucial role in coordinating activities such as adoption of sustainable farming practices (blue dots in the figure) and connection with local communities and retailers (purple dots in the figure).

Insights from economic experiments further underline this importance: miscomprehension of novel AES can reduce farmers’ conservation efforts, but Facilitators are well positioned to improve understanding, provide tailored advice, and create low-cost opportunities for exchanging lessons learned. Moreover, participants’ beliefs about their peers’ conservation behaviour were shown to strongly shape their own choices, pointing to the role of descriptive norms. Facilitators can help

nurture such norms within a Cluster by building trust, promoting the visibility of conservation efforts, and reinforcing the feasibility of collective action.

Policy implications

Successful Farmer Clusters depend on a number of interlinked factors related to facilitation, trust, the way in which advice is provided, evidence of impact, knowledge, guidance and financial support. Evidence from the FRAMEwork project across Europe highlights how these elements can work together to drive long-term conservation outcomes.

- **Skilled facilitation is essential**

Facilitators are the linchpins of effective Farmer Clusters. They coordinate meetings, deliver training, monitor progress, and connect farmers with NGOs, researchers, and policymakers. Where facilitation was strong, trust and peer learning flourished; where it was weak, engagement declined. Well-resourced Facilitators are vital for building cohesion, sustaining motivation, and ensuring lasting impact. Facilitators are most effective when locally embedded and professionally equipped, while structured and recurring activities—rather than ad-hoc events—are key to building trust, coherence, and collective action. Training and capacity-building should further professionalise Facilitators, enabling them to manage conflict, guide planning, and connect Clusters with expert advice, funding, and local networks. (Bohnet et al., 2025). Policy must prioritise investment in Facilitator training and support to maintain momentum and avoid fragmentation.

- **Facilitation Fund contract durations**

Facilitation funding contracts for Farmer Clusters need to be 5-10 years in length to support skilled Facilitators to build stronger relationships and trust with farmers, enable long-term environmental planning and thus the delivery of long-term benefits for biodiversity and rural communities. Team-based facilitation can combine essential skills in trust-building, technical support, and organisation, but one coordinator must remain responsible to avoid fragmented responsibilities (Bohnet et al., 2025). Many of the Farmer Clusters established through the FRAMEwork project felt that the establishment of trust was a significant driver of success, which often took a minimum of four years to establish.

- **Provision of one-to-one and group advice**

Allowing facilitation funding to fund a mixture of one-to-one advice (e.g. for technical planning and grant applications) and group advice (e.g. to address broad topics such as landscape habitat connectivity) would maximise impact by improving farmer engagement, learning and environmental outcomes.

- **Financial support for biodiversity monitoring**

Including support for landscape scale monitoring and evidence gathering is also recommended. This would allow group members to see the effects of their efforts on the ground and increases confidence that Farmer Clusters will be supported in the future.

- **Access to knowledge, advice, and practical tools**

Farmers need more than goodwill—they need the right information at the right time. Platforms like Recodo.io provide open-access training, biodiversity monitoring protocols, and stakeholder engagement resources that empower both Facilitators and farmers. These tools enable the adoption of biodiversity-friendly practices and align local actions with broader conservation goals. Policy should ensure that such platforms are widely accessible, regularly updated, and tailored to local contexts.

- **Incentives that support voluntary, collective action**

Incentives are most effective when they respect farmers’ autonomy, offer degrees of freedom in engagement and foster collaboration. FRAMEwork findings show that schemes with voluntary collaboration consistently outperform mandatory Farmer Cluster participation (Fritschle et al., 2025a, 2025b). Clusters saw higher engagement when incentives allowed flexible participation and supported peer-led initiatives. Collective result-based payments enhanced conservation outcomes and built peer accountability. Particularly in high-risk settings, collective payments improved cooperation by leveraging the potential for collective risk-sharing. Policymakers should design incentive structures that are adaptable, locally relevant, and rooted in shared goals.

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